

WAYS TO ENSURE MACROECONOMIC STABILITY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article highlights that macroeconomic stability is a key determinant of a country's economic growth, and that macroeconomic stability means low inflation and a competitively stable real exchange rate.

Key words. Macroeconomic stability, investment, economic reforms, economic growth, inflation, unemployment rate.

Many factors affect the development of the country's economy. Investments are the most important of these factors. That is, investments have a positive effect on the development of the economy. As the volume of investments in the economy increases, the economy also develops in parallel.

In addition, investments are of great importance in ensuring macroeconomic stability in the country. Ensuring macroeconomic stability indicates that the economy is developing rapidly in this country.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, while defining the programmatic and targeted tasks that need to be implemented in the economy in 2020 and the following years, stated that "First of all, ensuring macroeconomic stability and curbing inflation in 2020 is our main task in the process of economic reforms" increases the need for macroeconomic stability.

Macroeconomic stability is the main factor determining the country's economic growth. Macroeconomic stability refers to a situation where inflation is low and the real exchange rate is competitively stable.

In general, investments can be defined as follows: "Investments are an important factor of economic growth and are made by individuals, legal entities, foreign legal entities and individuals for the purpose of restoring and increasing the fixed and working capital, expanding production capacity. are material and immaterial benefits and rights to them included in business activities and other types of activity objects that are not prohibited by the laws of individuals or the state, as well as capital investments made with the purpose of future profit from the existing accumulated capital.

There are several types of investments, of which foreign investments are of particular importance. Because domestic investment means the circulation of existing capital in the country, while foreign investment means that additional capital will enter the country from abroad.

That is why foreign investments are gaining great importance in ensuring macroeconomic stability. Macroeconomic stability is the main factor determining the country's economic growth. Macroeconomic stability means low inflation and a competitive real exchange rate.

Macroeconomic stability means stable development of the country's economy without disturbing the balance of the main macroeconomic indicators: real growth of the gross domestic product, inflation, exchange rate, unemployment rate, balance of payments, etc.

Macroeconomic stability represents the rapid development of the country's economy and the provision of macroeconomic balance in the country, and the main signs of macroeconomic stability are as follows:

- There are no problems in the distribution of income;
- Recorded in stable economic growth rates;
- Ensuring full employment in the country, i.e. minimum unemployment;
- Stability of domestic prices (inflation is not high);
- Existence of a strong balance of payments;
- The fact that the state budget deficit is normal compared to GDP;
- Stable currency exchange rate;

As mentioned above, the increase in the weight of investments indicates the improvement of the production potential in this country and the emergence of new industrial enterprises.

As a result, population employment will increase and the unemployment rate will decrease. This will be one of the main indicators of macroeconomic stability. The increase in the employment of the population leads to an increase in the income of the population. The increase in the income of the population is the main tool leading to economic growth. As the country's export potential develops based on investments, it has a positive effect on the country's economic indicators. The improvement of the country's export potential leads to the formation of a strong balance of payments in the country, and this also affects the formation of a stable currency exchange rate.

In recent years, the reforms carried out on a large scale in our country have not left out the economic sector. Many presidential decrees and legal documents have been adopted in this direction.

In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Uzbekistan-2030 strategy, ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth, in particular, doubling the size of the economy by 2030 "countries with an income above the average" the following measures were planned to be implemented in order to join the ranks.

- To increase the gross domestic product to 160 billion dollars and income per capita to 4 thousand dollars;
- Ensuring macroeconomic stability and economic development with the necessary level of energy, water and infrastructure resources;
- Ensuring annual inflation at the level of 5-6 percent by 2030 by continuing structural reforms aimed at mutual coordination of monetary and credit, fiscal and foreign trade policies and improving the competitive environment in the market of goods and services;
- Consistent continuation of transformation and institutional reforms in the economy, ensuring a favorable investment and business environment in the country, and implementing a balanced monetary policy;
- Implementation of the medium-term public debt management strategy so that the ratio of public debt to GDP does not exceed 50 percent;

- To ensure an average annual growth of 7% in the volume of investments in fixed capital.

The measures taken to ensure macroeconomic stability, liberalize the currency market, introduce market methods of selling highly liquid goods, support and encourage entrepreneurship in our republic are favorable conditions for actively involving large segments of the population in entrepreneurial activities. created conditions and created a solid ground for consistent continuation of economic reforms.

Implementation of deep structural changes in economic sectors, accelerating the process of transition to a competitive market economy by forming a high-quality market of goods and services, improving and strengthening the system of social protection of the population, and introducing market principles in the management of state assets are of great importance in the new stage of the country's economic development. is enough.

- Maintaining macroeconomic stability, conducting an effective fiscal policy, fundamentally reforming the taxation system and tax administration;
- Acceleration of the process of the republic's transition to a competitive market economy based on the widespread introduction of market principles in the distribution of basic resources;
- To strengthen the system of social protection of citizens and the provision of state services to them, to increase the scope and types of protection of the population in need of social assistance;
- To further increase the efficiency of the public administration system, to develop the private sector and to support business entities;
- Increasing the efficiency of natural resource use, ensuring environmental protection, improving water resources management, and modernizing irrigation and land reclamation systems.

The role of foreign investments in ensuring macroeconomic stability in Uzbekistan is clearly visible, but this requires a proportionate and strategic approach. Continuous efforts to create an attractive investment climate, eliminate associated risks, and promote sustainable development are critical to maximizing the benefits of foreign investment for the country's long-term stability and prosperity.

In conclusion, we can say that investments are the main factor that develops the country's economy and ensures macroeconomic stability in the country. Based on this, increasing the volume of investments in the economy of Uzbekistan today is considered one of the most important urgent issues. The increase in the volume of investments indicates the construction of new enterprises, the modernization of existing ones, the emergence of new types of products, and the strengthening of competition. Based on this, investments are of great importance in ensuring the macroeconomic stability of the country.

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